

Enabling Interoperability in Steel Construction – New Concepts for Using IFC for Steel Fabrication

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ABSTRACT

In steel fabrication, DSTV-NC is the de facto standard for a machine-independent description of a (single) piece. The interface is used worldwide and ensures a uniform and comprehensive definition of component and processing information for software products and CNC systems. The interface is primarily designed for subtractive fabrication processes, however, new requirements regarding extended machining capabilities, assembly processes or feedback strategies for process information are not considered. Digitalisation and automation in steel construction are providing new potential for linking fabrication processes. The interconnection of digital information can create added value along the entire steel construction value chain, from planning to fabrication and assembly.

Building Information Modelling (BIM) stands for the idea of a continuous use of digital building models for the complete lifecycle of constructions, from planning and construction to operation, demolition and even reintegration. This methodology aims at a consecutive flow and enrichment of information to create significant increases in productivity and minimisation of errors in construction projects. While the methodology is already widely used in construction planning phases, the application of BIM in steel fabrication processes is not very common.

To exchange building information in a neutral and standardised way, buildingSMART International develops the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). The IFC data model is intended to cover all phases and processes of the architecture, engineering and construction industry and will be frequently updated and extended. This paper describes in a first step concepts how existing DSTV-NC capabilities can be mapped to IFC for a coherent hand-over of information between steps in the process chain, enabling the link between design and fabrication data.

Keywords: Steel Fabrication, BIM, IFC, DSTV-NC, MVD, mvdXML, Digitalisation

1 INTRODUCTION

In steel fabrication, DSTV-NC (German Steel Association - Numeric Control) serves as the universally accepted standard for providing a machine-independent representation of an individual steel part. This standard is employed world-wide, ensuring a consistent interface for Computer Aided Design (CAD) / Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAM) applications and Numerical Control (NC) fabrication (1,2). Today, however, there is a need for a constant flow of information from

design and pre-fabrication to on-site assembly and the dismantling and reuse phases of construction (3). The DSTV-NC format is limited in its ability to represent the life cycle of a steel structure, the bidirectional flow of information and the ability to incorporate new information required for new fabrication processes. The steel construction industry faces challenges such as shortage of skilled workers, cost and time constraints, and increased quality standards (4,5). In addition, flexible automation solutions in fabrication and especially in labour-intensive assembly impose new requirements on a data interface that ensures interoperability in different product life cycle phases. The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), a data model from buildingSMART, aim to be able to represent all phases of the product life cycle of a structure.

This paper outlines concepts for aligning existing DSTV-NC capabilities with IFC to facilitate the seamless transfer of information between different stages of the process chain. This link aims to bridge the gap between design and fabrication data. It provides the basis for interoperability in steel construction, embedded in the entire construction life cycle, by providing the data and information for all subsequent processes in a findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable format (6).

2 OVERVIEW OF DSTV-NC AND IFC

There are a number of approaches that promote interoperability in steel construction. The best known is the CIMSteel Integration Standard including Release 2 CIS/2, developed by the American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC) (7,8). In early 2000, studies were undertaken to evaluate the IFC and CIS/2 standards to support process modelling in the steel supply chain (9–11). Previous research has not focused on interoperability in steel construction, using IFC for steel fabrication to meet the requirements of Industry 4.0. This research focuses on the limitations of the widely used DSTV-NC standard, and the potential of IFC to meet the requirements.

2.1 DSTV-NC

In structural steelwork, DSTV-NC is the neutral industry standard for the description of a single piece. It has been developed as a link between CAD and steel processing machines (1). The DSTV-NC format encompasses solely the information necessary for fabrication, consisting of identification details and explicit geometry of a single part. It does not include CAD parametric data or machine-related information. All the major players in the industry have implemented interfaces to read/write DSTV-NC. Up to version 8, DSTV-NC files are ASCII based. Version 9 introduces a XML syntax but has rarely been implemented by industry. Apart from minor additions, versions 8 and 9 are identical in terms of content. In the past, the simplicity of DSTV-NC was a key to its success. Today, the steel construction industry needs more. Processes are designed and controlled in a growing data infrastructure. Cutting and assembly need to be linked by data. Data needs to be captured and shared, and it is much more than just part geometry. A successor data model to DSTV-NC that meets the requirements of modern fabrication and information technologies is needed to enable the link to digitalisation and automation in steel construction.

2.2 IFC

The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) are an open standard in the construction industry for the digital description of the built environment (buildings, bridges, etc.) throughout its lifecycle. The IFC data model is developed by buildingSMART and is registered by ISO as an international standard (12,13). The IFC model generally consists of objects, relations and property sets, the so-called entities. Entities describe, for example, spatial structures, components, materials and relationships between components. As the model is extensive and constantly evolving, specific views of the model are defined for specific use cases, the Model View Definitions (MVD) (14). The AISC defined an IFC2x3 model view called Exchange Module 11 (EM11) for steel fabrication back in 2012 (15). Although Tekla Structure and AutoCAD Advanced Steel support this model view definition, there are no known applications where IFC models have been directly imported into steel

processing machines. However, the EM11 Model View Definition provides a very good basis for further development.

The IFC standard provides a solid foundation for overcoming the limitations of the DSTV-NC standard by representing the existing DSTV-NC information, but also providing the structure for adding steel specifications and associated fabrication requirements. As a comprehensive Building Information Model, IFC has the theoretical ability to cover the entire life cycle of a steel structure, including the complete fabrication phase.

3 METHDOLOGY

As a first step, this paper outlines the concepts for mapping existing DSTV-NC capabilities to IFC to enable the seamless transfer of information between different stages of the process chain. This will provide a link between design and fabrication data. The aim is to take the information currently presented in the DSTV-NC format and present it in the IFC standard. The main objective is to take existing elements of the IFC4x3 schema and map them with the information that needs to be transferred from DSTV-NC to develop a model view definition for steel fabrication. During the study and development phase it was investigated that not all steel fabrication specifications are covered by the standard IFC elements. To be able to describe all the steel properties and to allow digital flow, existing IFC syntax is applied for specific steel fabrication properties.

3.1 Preliminary Scope

Figure 1 shows the covered scope of this paper. In the life cycle of steel construction, this is only a small but important phase. The starting point in the process chain being considered is structural planning, although data may already be available here, e.g. from the architecture. The information is then enriched and passed on in each subsequent process step. In this case , this results in three use cases: 1. Steel Construction Detailing, 2. Steel Fabrication Preparation and 3. Steel Fabrication Documentation.

Figure 1. Process Overview and Use Case description for interoperability in steel fabrication.

3.2 Use cases within this scope

The first use case describes the exchange of information and IFC models that must be available at the start of fabrication and must be provided by the designing party (CAD). In terms of content, this

involves the replacement and expansion of the DSTV-NC interface as well as the DSTV parts list interface. The second use case describes the exchange of information and IFC models that are transferred from work preparation to the workplace (e.g. steel processing machines). The last use case describes the exchange of information and IFC models that are transferred back from steel processing back for documentation.

3.3 Approaches for the technical Realisation

The general way to define a Model View Definition (MVD), i.e. a domain-specific view of the IFC schema, as specified by buildingSMART, is to define an IDM (Information Delivery Manual), a standardised methodology developed by buildingSMART for describing information requirements (16). An IDM essentially describes the level of information required by those involved in a BIM project at a specific point in time or work process. The use cases presented here have been developed in deviation from this formal process, as the primary aim was to implement a demonstrator in a dynamic development process and thus provide proof of concept. The formal description of an IDM will also be realised as part of the further development of the IFC Steel Fabrication View.

4 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE REQUIREMENTS WITH IFC

The requirements resulting from the use cases are implemented using the latest IFC version, IFC4x3 (17). As IFC schema changes can only be implemented with a new IFC version, only existing entities and concepts were used. In order to ensure the best possible interoperability, the concepts were frequently compared with the IFC 4 Reference Model View (18). In contrast to schema changes and extensions, IFC allows the user to define arbitrary property sets with user-defined properties. When defining new property sets, the existing EM11 property sets (15) were analysed and, where necessary, harmonised, specified and supplemented. The concept for an IFC Steel Fabrication View is described in detail below. They are divided into the following categories: Structure, Entities, Local Placements, Geometry, Material and Property Sets. It is not yet a formal Model View Definition (MVD) and only a few concepts are currently formalised as mvdXML for testing.

4.1 Structure (Spatial and Assembly)

In principle, there are no restrictions on the spatial structure of the IFC model. IFC allows buildings with or without floors, bridges, roads and railways with a corresponding subdivision or, if not specified, facilities. For fabrication, it is important to define fabrication units. The IFC entity `IfcElementAssembly` is used to aggregate all the parts of an assembly so that they can be uniquely identified. IFC has optional predefined assembly types, but these are not relevant to fabrication. Although IFC requires a globally unique identifier for `IfcElementAssembly`, this does not correspond to the usual conventions used in steel construction. Therefore, a property set for an identification system that meets the requirements of steel construction is mandatory for an assembly.

4.2 IFC Entities

The basic elements for steel construction such as beam column, member and plate are already defined in IFC. Analogous to the assemblies, the globally unique identifier does not correspond to the identification system of the steel structure. Therefore, a property set is also required for identification here. Fabrication processes such as sawing, drilling and milling are usually material-removing. Up to now, these machining features were modelled as `IfcOpeningElement`. With version 4, IFC introduced the entity `IfcVoidingFeature`, which corresponds semantically perfectly to machining features. In addition, the predefined element type can specify the voiding feature in more detail, for example as CUTOUT, HOLE, MITER, and NOTCH. As the `IfcVoidingFeature` contains fabrication information in the attached property sets, any machining operation, including sawing, must be represented by this element. *Figure 2* shows an example of a beam where corresponding

IfcVoidingFeature elements are visible and coloured according to the predefined type (grey = NOTCH, blue = CUTOOUT, black = HOLE).

Figure 2. Example of a beam: unprocessed beam (left), beam with IfcVoidingFeature elements colored by the predefined type - grey = NOTCH, blue = CUTOOUT, black = HOLE (middle) and the final beam (right).

The IFC model supports storing common information for objects in object types. By defining an object type with corresponding property sets and optionally with geometry, common properties and geometry can be easily assigned to multiple instances of an object. This concept can significantly reduce the size of an IFC model and additionally simplifies the identification of identical parts.

4.3 Local Placements

IFC models are usually structured hierarchically and the position of the IFC elements always refers to the next higher hierarchical level using local placements. Figure 3 on the left shows a typical hierarchy tree with the corresponding local placements and the necessary relations between the elements to build the hierarchy tree. Due to the tolerances in steel construction, however, it is not sufficient to know the position of a machining element in relation to the element to be processed, but it is important to identify a reference point and a direction from which to measure. To attach additional information to an element, IFC provides the IfcAnnotation element. This element can be integrated into the IFC hierarchy tree, has a local placement and can be represented by any geometry. Figure 3 on the right shows the integration of an IfcAnnotation element in the hierarchy tree and the structure of the local placements. By definition, the xy plane of the local placement of the IfcAnnotation element is the reference plane and the z direction is the measurement direction.

Figure 3. Hierarchy tree and local placement structure of an IFC model without IfcAnnotation (left) and with IfcAnnotation (right).

Although the geometry is optional and is not required for the coordinate transformation, it may be useful to create a geometry that represents the reference plane for the visual representation. The coordinate transformation depends only on the local placements of the machining feature (IfcVoidingElement), the associated annotation (IfcAnnotation) and the element to be processed (e.g. IfcBeam). Figure 4 shows the relation between the local placements. The annotation defines from which side the measurement for drilling the hole must be taken to ensure that the tolerances are correctly accounted for.

Figure 4. The relations of the local placements without consideration of the tolerance influences (left) and with consideration (right)

4.4 Geometry

The geometry of the basic elements Beam, Column and Member must be created as extrusions of parametric profiles such as I-, T-, or L-Shape. This is necessary because the type and name of the profile definition (e.g. HE 400B) determines the shape of the unprocessed part. If the machining is performed in a plane, the *IfcVoidingFeature* elements must also be represented as extrusions. In this case, however, all profiles available in IFC are permitted.

4.5 Material

As the work pieces in steel construction usually consist of a homogeneous material, *IfcMaterial* should be used to represent the intended material. *IfcMaterial* requires a name and optionally a description and a category. To determine the material, the material grade (e.g. S355JR) must be specified in the name and the material itself (e.g. Steel Aluminium) must be specified as the category. If another comparable material is selected in the work preparation, the actual material used is then saved in a property set.

4.6 Property Sets

As previously mentioned, the EM11 Model View Definition for IFC 2x3 already contains a number of property sets. In principle, the property sets can be grouped into sets for the identification and administration of parts and sets for processing-relevant information. The property sets for identification and administration contain properties such as assembly and part identification, piece and main piece identification, customer and shipping information.

As an example of processing-relevant information, the property set for holes is described in detail here. EM11 provides a property set for round holes and an additional property set for slotted holes. The property set for round holes consists only of a type specification (*BeveledHole*, *TappedHole* and *ThreadedHole*), the hole diameter and information on whether it is a through hole or a blind hole. As this generalisation does not allow for all necessary fabrication processes, the round hole is categorised into through hole, threaded hole, blind hole and sink hole. Consequently, there is a separate property set definition for each category. The through hole property set contains all the properties relevant for processing a basic hole: coordinate reference, coordinates with respect to that reference, diameter and optional information on which fabrication processes are permitted or prohibited. The threaded hole property set also contains the thread direction, the thread type, the thread gradient and optionally the thread depth. The blind hole property set only requires a mandatory hole depth in addition to the base hole. The sinkhole property set includes the base hole, the sink angle and the sink depth.

4.7 Model View Definition XML (mvdXML)

For the formal description of MVDs and checking rules, buildingSMART provides the mvdXML standard, which was created as part of IFC4 development in 2013 (19). Although mvdXML is no longer being officially developed by buildingSMART (the current version is mvdXML 1.1), mvdXML version 1.2 is used as the basis for the development of the current schema version

IFC4x3 and for MVD based software certification (20). The use of the new Information Delivery Specification (IDS) standard by buildingSMART was not sufficient for the use cases presented here, as more complex checks such as the level of detail of the geometry or technical contradictions are excluded and the focus is placed on the most important alphanumeric model information (21,22). The scope of the defined rule sets is illustrated by a simple example of checking the profile geometry of an extrusion profile to ensure that only parametric profile geometries are used. First, the context in which the rule is to be applied is determined. For example, the check rules are to be applied to all elements of type IfcBeam. The actual check rules are then as follows:

1. *The used geometry must be a swept solid*
2. *The profile of the solid must be a parametrised profile*

This check is only successful if both conditions are fulfilled. The KITModelViewer application developed at KIT enables both editing of checking rules and the checking of IFC datasets. The defined rules are provided in mvdXML format as part of the KITModelViewer distribution (23).

5 DSTV-DEMONSTRATOR

As part of a feasibility study, Use Cases 1 and 2 were implemented to investigate the information flow from CAD to a steel processing machine (see *Figure 5*). The demonstrator has been employed to illustrate the framework conditions, advantages, disadvantages, and the repercussions for the involved stakeholders.

*manually extended; ** fully automatic generated; *** in preparation

Figure 5. Workflow of DSTV-Demonstrator.

For CAD as the data supplier, the impact is minimal as the required data is inherently available. The main requirement is to ensure that the specifications for the specific IFC format are adhered to during data transfer. Conversely, the integration of IFC into Production Planning Software (PPS) is still in its infancy, with significant implications and opportunities. IFC introduces unique identifiers (GUIDs) for both parts and individual geometric features, offering new ways to provide accurate feedback to the final Building Information Model. The implications for fabrication are significant. Parts are created incrementally, with stock materials cut to size and intermediate products moved between workstations and machines, each with its own specific tasks. Traditionally, PPS systems have managed this process individually and opaquely. IFC modelling now provides a standardised basis for each stage of fabrication. GUIDs allow features such as holes and slots to be precisely addressed, facilitating seamless communication between PPS and machines. IFCs provide an ideal basis for continually adding machining data to the model, ensuring transparency for external evaluation software. Despite the higher cost of IFC modelling, especially for simpler processes, the authors argue that the benefits outweigh the drawbacks.

The following case was implemented in the DSTV-Demonstrator:

First, a design model was transferred from CAD to a PPS system using IFC. Both the IFC data from the CAD and the IFC data generated by the PPS are checked using the KITModelViewer software (see *Figure 6*).

Figure 6. IFC data generated by the CAD are checked using the KITModelViewer.

The PPS Software (by Huhn EDV Beratung) then validates the data, identifies the components to be processed and devises the necessary fabrication processes. One such process is beam fabrication, in which the raw form of the shorter, usable parts is cut from longer stock bars. PPS systems improve material usage efficiency by strategically distributing these parts among the available stock bars through a process known as "nesting". The result is good parts, scrap and possibly a remnant bar derived from the original stock bar. The visual representation in *Figure 7* shows good parts in blue, scrap in grey and remnants in green.

Figure 7. The IFC model of the good part (blue), enriched by the PPS system is then sent to the machine.

After the steel processing preparation and the implementation of the IFC into the PPS for detailed machine allocation, the IFC with the nested parts is exported and sent to the machine. KALTENBACH GmbH + Co. KG has implemented an interface for the IFC so that the machine can extract the important information from the IFC and generate the CNC code. This code is essential for the operation of the machine and the machining of the part. *Figure 8* shows the 3D visualisation of the beam on the machine control station, based on the imported IFC. In fact, the work preparation can only give an indication of beam's dimensions. The actual size is measured on the machine before machining. In the future, the aim is to write back the actual measured geometries and process information. Compared to the existing DSTV, a more precise description is now possible, allowing detailed fabrication processes. In addition to direct machine instructions, other information and data can be linked to the fabricated parts, such as real measurements and standardised feedback for documentation. The DSTV demonstrator was successfully processed according to the workflow shown in *Figure 5*. *Figure 9* shows the processing of the beam based on the transfer of DSTV-NC information to the IFC representation.

Figure 8. Visualisation of the beam on the Kaltenbach machine interface, based on the imported IFC.

Figure 9. Processed beam on Kaltenbach machine.

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The successful demonstration of the applicability of the IFC format in steel fabrication is an important step forward. The transition from the DSTV-NC representation to the IFC representation of the required steel fabrication information enables interoperability within the industry. By implementing concrete definitions and requirements based on the existing IFC schema and using an exemplary case study, important lessons have been learned. These form the basis for extending the transformation capabilities to other steel fabrication processes beyond drilling and cutting, the feasibility of which is being investigated intensively. The results obtained will be disseminated widely in the industry by presenting them to other companies in the steel construction software and steel construction machinery sectors in order to promote standardisation. Further research may also focus on demonstrating an extension of IFC and BIM towards semantic ontology description with a focus on human and machine readability (24).

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